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Molecule(s): protiated (^1H)-DNA plasmid; deuterated (^2H)-DNA plasmid

Construct: pFastBac1 empty vector (~ 4.8 kbp).

Yield & Purity:

- 1) protiated (^1H)-DNA plasmid in H_2O
- 2) deuterated (^2H)-DNA plasmid in D_2O

	Concentration $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$	A260/A280	Volume (mL)	Yield (μg)
^1H -DNA plasmid	196.6	1.94	9	~1700
^2H -DNA plasmid	102.9	2.03	13.8	~1350

0.8% Agarose gel in TAE buffer, 1 μg loaded of each.

[Lane 1: 1kb GeneRuler DNA Ladder Mix; Lane 3: ^1H -DNA plasmid; Lane 5: ^2H -DNA plasmid]

